

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

FIGURE S1. Basic statistics of the dataset, including proportions of missing data and number of loci in each sample’s assembly used for downstream analyses.

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FIGURE S2. Phylogenetic tree estimated using maximum likelihood and concatenated loci in RAxML-ng (Kozlov et al. 2019) for all samples (n=93), including samples from outgroup species *L. alterna* and *L. elapsoides*. Branch colors correspond to group assignment used for allele frequency and fixed difference analyses.

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FIGURE S4. Principal components analysis as implemented in the *adeigenet* package in R (Jombart 2008; Jombart and Ahmed 2011) for three subsets of data: all samples, including outgroup species *L. alterna* and *L. elapsoides* for a) PC1 and PC2, and b) PC1 and PC3 (n=93); all samples, excluding *L. elapsoides*, for c) PC1 and PC2, and d) PC1 and PC3 (n=90); and only Kansas–Missouri transect samples for e) PC1 and PC2, and f) PC1 and PC3 (n=85). Data points are colored based on collection locality or species (in the case of outgroups).

FIGURE S5. Results from the sNMF algorithm as implemented in the *LEA* package in R (Frichot and François 2014) for each data subset with entropy values for each K value. Five runs were performed for each K and each dataset: a) Samples from Kansas and Missouri, as well as *L. alternans* samples; and b) samples only from Kansas and Missouri.

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FIGURE S6. sNMF (Frichot and François 2014) results for $K=3$ from the analysis containing Kansas–Missouri samples and *L. alterna* individuals (n=90).

FIGURE S7. Results from conStruct (Bradburd et al. 2018) analysis for $K=2$ for Kansas–Missouri transect samples ($n=85$).

FIGURE S8. The maximum likelihood cline of average allele frequencies per group fitted using *HZAR* (Derryberry et al. 2014) across 44 loci diagnostic between reference groups (loci were considered diagnostic if the allele was different in at least 80% of individuals of the reference groups). The 95% confidence interval is shown in gray shading. Admixture index values for each individual are overlaid as colored data points; black data points indicate average longitudinally defined group values; distance was calculated from the average longitude of the reference west group.

FIGURE S9. The number of pairwise raw fixed differences for each sample, including outgroup samples (*L. alterna* and *L. elapsoides*) as implemented in the *dartR* package (Gruber et al. 2018). Assignment of samples to groups is indicated by colored bars next to sample numbers.

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FIGURE S10. The number of pairwise raw fixed differences for each group, including outgroup samples (*L. alternata* and *L. elapsoides*) as implemented in the *dartR* package (Gruber et al. 2018). Assignment of samples to groups is indicated by colored bars next to sample numbers.

a)

b)

c)

FIGURE S11. a) Potential *L. alterna* x *L. triangulum* hybrid individual (photo: Troy Hibbitts). Though coloration is consistent with b) typical *L. alterna* individuals (photo: Brittney A. White), note the distinct head and banding patterning more consistent with c) *L. triangulum* individuals (photo: Troy Hibbitts). All three individuals were collected from the Davis Mountains, Texas.